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Green Marketing Activities And Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Packaged Drinks In Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of green marketing indicators on consumer buying behaviour regarding packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The researcher considered indicators such as eco-friendly and recyclable packs, which were measured against consumer buying behaviour. The target population comprised all residents of Uyo, the state capital of Akwa Ibom State, who were assumed to have purchased some form of packaged drink, regarded as an infinite population. Slovin's formula was applied to determine a sample size of 400 respondents. The main source of data was primary, collected using a structured five-point Likert scale questionnaire. The data were analysed using simple linear regression at a 0.05 significance level. Findings showed that eco-friendly and recyclable packs have a positive and significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks. All null hypotheses were therefore rejected. It was recommended, among other things, that drink manufacturers should prioritise the use of recyclable packaging materials, especially plastics, as the quality of recycled plastic is a major factor influencing the market for drinks and causes little or no harm to the environment or the product itself.

Keywords: Green Marketing, Consumer Buying Behaviour, Akwa Ibom State

INTRODUCTION

Green marketing has received considerable attention from marketing academics, practitioners, and consumers in Nigeria over the past few decades. The concept began to gain prominence in academic circles during the late 1980s and early 1990s. The inaugural workshop on *Ecological Marketing* was conducted by the American Marketing Association (AMA) in 1975, and its contents were subsequently published as *Ecological Marketing* in a seminar publication on the subject (Akter, 2012).

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Globally, there has been a marked increase in consumer awareness and mindfulness regarding the consumption of goods and services. The depletion of natural resources and the resulting severe environmental damage have become major concerns (Chen and Chai, 2010). Significant consequences of environmental degradation include global warming, increased environmental pollution, and loss of biodiversity (Chen and Chai, 2010).

Similar to global trends, Nigerians are showing greater concern for environmental preservation. The core premise in understanding green marketing is that potential consumers perceive a product or service as “green” if it is environmentally friendly, safe, and socially responsible. Consequently, purchasing decisions may be influenced by this perception (Ebhote, 2019). To promote green marketing, regulatory agencies and legislation have been established in Nigeria to protect consumers from harmful products and ensure environmental safety (Rashad and Igbazua, 2011).

Substantial research has examined the effectiveness of green marketing on consumer purchasing. Some studies have tested the effect of eco-friendly products on brand image, while others have explored purchasing behaviours such as avoiding products deemed harmful or environmentally destructive. Rising health consciousness has also bolstered demand for packaged drinks, prompting manufacturers across major soft drink categories to diversify their portfolios.

In Nigeria, several green marketing studies have been conducted in different contexts and with various variables. Some have focused on organisational green strategies. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is limited empirical evidence on how green marketing proxies influence consumer buying behaviour for drinks specifically. This study therefore seeks to determine whether eco-friendly packs, recyclable packs, and product safety (safe for consumption)—as proxies of green marketing—are related to consumers' buying behaviour.

Objectives of the Study

While the main purpose of this study is to ascertain the level of association between green marketing indicators and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, the specific objectives were to:

- i. determine the influence that eco-friendly packs have on consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

- ii. ascertain the effect that recyclable packs have on consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Hypotheses of the Study

The hypotheses formulated to guide the study were:

H₀1: Eco-friendly packs do not significantly influence consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

H₀2: There is no significant effect between recyclable packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Concept of Green Marketing

The notion of green marketing has been examined across multiple domains of marketing, including social marketing, ecological marketing, environmental marketing, and sustainable marketing (Soonthonsmai, 2001; Chamorro and Tomas, 2006). Yan and Yazdanifard (2014) note that researchers contend the concept was initially formulated in the late 1970s. Mishra and Sharma (2012) describe green marketing as an emerging strategy encompassing various initiatives, such as adopting fair-trade practices, modifying products, implementing sustainable production processes, and using eco-friendly packaging. The American Marketing Association (AMA) defines green marketing as the distribution and promotion of products that do not adversely affect the environment (Yazdanifard and Mercy, 2011).

From an environmental perspective, green marketing involves organisational initiatives to produce, promote, package, and recycle products in ways that demonstrate awareness of, and responsiveness to, ecological concerns. Saini (2013) defines “green” as a holistic concept encompassing products and practices characterised by their organic qualities, sustainability, and general environmental friendliness. The study asserts that green marketing entails promoting and selling products or services by highlighting their beneficial environmental characteristics. Saini (2013) further posits that a good or service is considered environmentally friendly if it offers intrinsic ecological advantages or is produced and/or packaged through sustainable methods. Consumers often associate terms such as *phosphate-free*, *recyclable*, *refillable*, and *ozone-safe* with green marketing (Zulfiqar and Shafaat, 2015). This study focuses on

green marketing indicators in packaged beverages that may influence consumer purchasing behaviour, particularly environmentally friendly and recyclable packaging.

Environmental (Eco)-Friendly Packaging

The significance of packaging is paramount across various product categories, as it attracts and inspires customers to select products. The use of materials and manufacturing techniques that minimise energy consumption and environmental impact is noteworthy (Jerda and Sahayaselvi, 2018). Packaging plays a significant role in influencing the choice of environmentally friendly products. As noted by Dantas et al. (2004), labels and packaging elements are crucial factors affecting consumer decisions. Grönman et al. (2012) assert that the primary function of packaging is to protect and deliver the appropriate product to the correct end-user in a secure, economically viable, and accessible manner. Consequently, packaging safeguards products against external factors and potential damage, ensuring their security throughout the supply chain (González-García et al., 2016). Williams and Wikström (2011) further highlight the role of packaging in reducing food waste and mitigating the environmental impact of the entire food packaging system.

Conceptually, the eco-friendliness of a product's packaging refers to the design, development, and delivery of packaging that prioritises environmental sustainability, thereby minimising harm to the environment and its stakeholders (Zia, 2012). The use of plastics, chemicals, and non-biodegradable materials is associated with numerous adverse effects, underscoring the advocacy for eco-friendly packaging (Patel et al., 2018).

Suherlan and Widiyanti (2021) identify five fundamental principles of packaging design. First, packaging acts as a wrapper that encapsulates the product's identity and intended use. Second, it serves as a protective barrier against impact, friction, and shock, making material durability essential. Third, packaging should be user-friendly, providing a pleasant tactile experience, being gentle to the touch, flexible in grip, easy to maintain, convenient to store, and stable when positioned, with priority given to recyclability. Fourth, packaging should effectively showcase the product image and indicate market segmentation, incorporating creativity, aesthetic appeal, and imaginative vision. Packaging reflects the user's social standing and the contexts in which the product is used, with distinctiveness being a foremost consideration. Fifth, packaging should embody environmental harmony. Jerda and Sahayaselvi (2018)

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propose that the adoption of eco-friendly packaging by both manufacturers and consumers can reduce pollutants harmful to the atmosphere, soil, and oceans.

Prihandono et al. (2020) conducted a study in Indonesia examining the impact of green marketing tools, eco-friendly labels, and green advertising on consumer purchasing behaviour for mineral water. Using partial least squares analysis on data from 115 respondents, they found a positive and significant relationship between eco-friendly labelling and green advertising in influencing purchase decisions. They recommended that bottled water manufacturers implement green marketing campaigns targeting both regional and global markets to improve sales performance and address existing challenges.

Ishaswini and Datta (2011) conducted a study in India to assess consumers' environmental concerns, understanding of ecological issues, and awareness of sustainable products. The findings indicate that awareness of eco-friendly products and environmental concerns significantly influence green purchasing behaviour. The authors noted that packaging and labels capture consumer attention within seconds, yet it remains challenging for consumers to identify environmentally friendly products. Nevertheless, consumers demonstrate awareness of packaging attributes related to environmental considerations.

Recyclable Packs

Recycling entails the utilisation of reclaimed materials to produce a novel product (Hopewell et al., 2009). The incorporation of recycled materials in packaging presents significant advantages in terms of resource efficiency and reductions in carbon emissions. The extent of resources conserved and carbon emissions mitigated is contingent upon the proportion of recycled materials integrated within the packaging application and the recovery techniques utilised (British Plastics Federation – BPF, 2020). As articulated by Mostafa (2007), the acquisition of recyclable packaging products that pose no detriment to the environment constitutes a manifestation of environmentally conscious purchasing behaviour.

Materials utilised for packaging, including papers, paper boards, plastics, steel cans, and glass jars, serve the essential function of enclosing or safeguarding products throughout the processes of distribution, storage, sale, delivery, and utilisation. The selection and application of these packaging materials are contingent upon the nature of

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the products, associated costs, and the intended purpose of the packaging (Jang et al., 2020). Recyclable packaging utilised for beverages may manifest in the following forms:

- i. **Paper and cardboard packaging:** Packaging made from paper and carton board demonstrates a high degree of recyclability. Nonetheless, the recycling of paper packaging is not an infinite process, as the fibres diminish in length and strength with each cycle of recycling (Kazulytė and Kruopienė, 2018).
- ii. **Plastic packaging:** Plastics are utilised globally due to their safety in the packaging of food, beverages, pharmaceuticals, and products for children.
- iii. **Glass packaging:** Glass packaging boasts an impressive recyclability rate approaching 100% and can undergo recycling processes indefinitely, maintaining its purity and quality with minimal degradation (Kazulytė and Kruopienė, 2018). Glass can be reused with confidence, as its chemical composition remains stable and does not leach in to other substances. Consequently, glass recycling operates as a closed-loop system, generating neither supplementary waste nor products (Padmalatha and Shresta, 2016).
- iv. **Metal packaging:** Metal packages possess the remarkable ability to be recycled indefinitely without any degradation in quality, ensuring that there is no occurrence of "down cycling" of materials; they seamlessly integrate into the material-to-material loop (Packaging Resources Action Group: PRAG, 2009).
- v. **Composite packaging:** While the individual elements constituting composite packaging may possess the technical capacity for recycling, the practical challenges associated with sorting and separating materials, such as laminates and metallised films, effectively hinder the feasibility of recycling in real-world applications (Kazulytė and Kruopienė, 2018).

In 2019, Boateng conducted a study in Ghana aimed at identifying the factors related to packaging that affect consumer purchasing behaviour within the soft drink sector in Accra. The analysis of data gathered from 220 soft drink consumers in Accra indicates that plastic bottle packaging occupies the foremost position, followed by aluminium cans in second place, paper packaging in third, and glass bottle packaging in fourth, reflecting the preferences within the soft drink industry in Accra, Ghana. The research

reveals a noteworthy correlation between packaging and consumer purchasing behaviour. In light of the findings, it is advisable for soft drink manufacturers to focus on utilising plastic, aluminium cans, and paper as packaging options to effectively shape consumer purchasing behaviour, while simultaneously minimising the reliance on glass bottle packaging. Recycling serves as an evident strategy for waste management; however, it also exemplifies the application of industrial ecology in contemporary practice (Hopewell et al., 2009).

Consumer Buying Behaviour towards Packaged Drinks

Investigating consumer behaviour is crucial for comprehending the intricacies of product consumption and the various elements influencing the purchasing process of packaged goods (Santos et al., 2018). The dynamics of consumer buying behaviour extend beyond the mere act of purchasing products; it encompasses a comprehensive spectrum of activities, ranging from the initial recognition of a problem to the subsequent evaluation of experiences and ideas aimed at fulfilling their needs and desires (Mohamed et al. 2018). Consumer behaviour encompasses the examination of the processes engaged in the selection, acquisition, utilisation, or disposal of goods, services, ideas, or experiences by individuals, groups, and organisations, all aimed at fulfilling the needs and desires of consumers (Solomon et al. 2007). Kotler and Keller (2015) emphasise the significance of comprehending consumer buying behaviour, which is crucial for both manufacturers and service providers. The methods by which customers select products can greatly influence competitive advantage over rivals in numerous respects.

As environmental concerns increasingly resonate with the public, enterprises have started to adapt their production methods, the generation of goods or services, and, as a result, their marketing strategies. Organisations have commenced the production of sustainable and eco-conscious products.(Boztepe, 2012).Furthermore, enhancing the comprehension of consumer behaviour regarding environmentally friendly products is crucial, given the significant expansion of such products across all consumer sectors due to the prevailing 'green shift' and the strategic marketing approaches employed by numerous organisations.(Durif, Roy, and Boivin, 2012).

The green consumer is characterised as an individual who embraces environmentally conscious practices and opts for eco-friendly products in place of conventional alternatives. Furthermore, environmentally conscious consumers exhibit

a profound concern regarding the ecological ramifications stemming from their purchasing decisions. This category of consumers often believes that every individual, along with governments, businesses, and environmental advocates, has a significant role to play in consumerism and bears responsibility for environmental stewardship (Boztepe, 2012). Consequently, the assortment of products significantly influences the recognition of environmental sustainability and attributes of the product, potentially shaping consumer behaviour during the purchasing process.

As noted by Quazi (2008), the phenomenon of consumer buying behaviour, often termed 'consumerism', encompasses both micro and macro aspects of consumerist concerns. The micro-consumerist concerns encompass matters such as misbranding practices, misleading advertisements, deceptive packaging, and unfair pricing, among others. The overarching concerns of consumerism primarily engage with larger contexts such as environmental degradation, healthcare systems, nuclear opposition, and similar matters.

Conceptually, the framework for this study on green marketing indicators and consumer buying behaviour is presented as:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Green Marketing and Consumer Buying Behaviour

Source: *The Researcher's Construct (2023).*

Theoretical Framework

This study was fundamentally grounded in the theory of reasoned action. This social theory was formulated by Icek Ajzen and Martin Fishbein in 1975 and subsequently refined in 1980, as detailed in their publication "Understanding attitudes and predicting social behaviour: Attitudes, intentions, and perceived behavioural control." The theory aims to elucidate the

mechanisms through which attitudes exert influence over behaviour. The components that constitute the Theory of Reasoned Action include behavioural beliefs, assessments of behavioural outcomes that culminate in attitude, followed by normative beliefs and the motivation to comply, which together form subjective norms. The interplay between attitude and subjective norm culminates in the intention to engage in the behaviour, ultimately manifesting in the behaviour itself. This is represented in their model on Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Theory of Reasoned Action – TRA (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; 1980)

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Theory-of-Reasoned-Action-TRA-Fishbein-Ajzen-1975_fig1_284014676

It is essential to recognise that while the theory of reasoned action posits that behaviours are solely shaped by intentions, other scholarly works indicate that attitudes and prior actions have a direct impact on future behaviour (Bargh, 1997; Bentler and Speckart, 1979). This perspective suggests that an individual's present actions may be ingrained and elicited spontaneously by external cues.

This study elucidates how the theory of reasoned action provides insight into the mechanisms behind consumer product choices, particularly as they are influenced by environmental stimuli. Their awareness of the green attributes depicted on the product packaging influences their assessment of the product as environmentally friendly, potentially shaping their purchasing intentions and behavioural attitudes.

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METHODOLOGY

This study employed a survey research design approach. The research was conducted in Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom, with a population of 1,265,000 residents. The target respondents comprised individuals who consume or purchase packaged beverages of various types, representing a defined demographic within this population. The application of Slovin's Formula, set at a 5% margin of error, facilitated the determination of a suitable sample size for the study, maintaining a confidence level of 95%. The utilisation of the formula yielded a result of 399.8, which was rounded to approximately 400 and subsequently adopted as the sample size for the study. The study utilised a simple random sampling technique, and data were gathered through a survey questionnaire employing a five-point Likert scale.

The components of the research instrument underwent scrutiny by fellow scholars within the marketing discipline to assess both face validity and content validity. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability test was conducted as a preliminary assessment to evaluate the internal consistency of the items within the research instrument. The estimations of dependability that were acquired exceeded the 0.50 threshold, prompting us to advance with the analyses. The resulting coefficients of the items are summarised in Table 1 from Appendix I:

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha reliability Co-efficient of study variables

S/No.	Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
1	Eco-friendly	3	0.922
2	Recyclable packs	3	0.667
3	Consumer buying behaviour	4	0.753
Total		10	0.781

Source: Data Analysis Output, 2023.

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DATA ANALYSIS

A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed to consumers of packaged drinks within the study area, of which 362 were retrieved and deemed usable, resulting in a response rate of 91 percent. The responses were subsequently analysed utilising the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 25.0). The descriptive characteristics of respondents are shown on Table 2:

Table 2: Descriptive Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
<u>Age</u>		
20-30 years	86	23.8
31-40 years	101	27.9
41-50 years	89	24.6
51 years and above	86	23.8
Total	362	100.0
<u>Gender of respondent</u>		
Male	193	54.1
Female	166	45.9
Total	362	100.0
<u>Educational Qualification</u>		
SSCE	72	19.9
Diploma/OND and Equivalent	98	27.1
HND/BSc/BA and Equivalent	103	28.5
Post Graduate and Equivalent	89	24.6
Total	362	100.0
<u>Attention to Environmental signs</u>		
Yes	191	52.8
No	171	47.2
	362	

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Total		
Frequency of Purchase		
Frequently	212	58.6
Occasionally (Depending on the product)	150	41.4
Total	362	100.0

Source: The Researcher's Compilation (2023).

Table 2 shows that shoppers/consumers aged 31–40 years (27.9%) constituted the largest proportion of respondents, followed by those aged 41–50 years (24.6%), 20–30 years (23.8%), and 51 years and above (23.8%). The results also indicate that 193 males (54.1%) participated in the study, compared with 166 females (45.9%). The table further reveals that 103 respondents (28.5%) possessed an HND, BSc, BA, or equivalent qualification, while 98 respondents (27.1%) held a Diploma, OND, or equivalent. In addition, 89 respondents (24.6%) had a postgraduate qualification or equivalent, and 72 respondents (19.9%) possessed a Senior Secondary Certificate (O'Level) as their highest educational attainment.

The implication of these results is that the study was gender-inclusive, and all participants were sufficiently educated to comprehend the subject under study and provide informed responses to the survey questions. When asked whether they paid close attention to environmental signs and messages on product packaging while shopping, 191 respondents (52.8%) indicated that they did, while 171 (47.2%) acknowledged being aware of such messages but not paying close attention to them while shopping.

Respondents were also asked how often they purchased packaged drinks of any kind (including bottled, canned, and paper-packed water, soft drinks, alcoholic drinks, juice, and similar beverages). The results showed that 212 respondents (58.6%) frequently purchased packaged drinks, while 150 respondents (41.4%) purchased them occasionally, depending on the product and the need. The implication of this finding is that all respondents were familiar with the research topic and could relate to the subject matter.

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Test of Hypotheses

H₀1: Eco-friendly packs do not significantly influence consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3 : Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.792 ^a	.628	.627	1.44601

a. Predictors: (Constant), Eco-Friendly

Table 4: ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1270.883	1	1270.883	607.8	.000 ^b
	Residual	752.744	360	2.091		
	Total	2023.627	361			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Eco-Friendly

Table 5: Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.540	.406		3.790	.000
	Eco-Friendly	.846	.034	.792	24.654	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behaviour

Source: *The Researcher's Computation (2023).*

Results from the table show that the independent variable 'eco-friendly packs' ($X_1 = Ef$) explained approximately 63% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks with an $R^2 = 0.628$. This means that eco-friendly packs, considered as a green marketing indicator, were able to account for 63% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour. The result reveals that the relationship between eco-friendly packs (Ef) and consumer buying behaviour (Cb) was very strong according to $R = 0.708$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.627$, indicating that the regression model of this study is said to have a very strong explanatory power of the dependent variable.

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In addition, the F-ratio = 607.800 and p-value < 0.000 on the ANOVA suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that eco-friendly packs significantly predicted the changes in the dependent variable (consumer buying behaviour). To evaluate the degree of change between the independent variable and the dependent variable, the value of the beta coefficients for eco-friendly packs (EF) had a statistically significant unstandardised coefficient of $\beta_{x1} = 0.846$ and p-value = 0.000, indicating a positive significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks. This finding can be interpreted to mean that every unit change in eco-friendly packs will result in a 0.846 increase in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks, all other factors being held constant. The resulting simple linear model is represented as:

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + e$$

$$Y = 1.540 + 0.846 X_1$$

$$Cb = 1.540 + 0.846 Ef$$

However, since the significant p-value is less than 0.05 (Sig. p-value=0.000<0.05), it is concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between eco-friendly packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

H₀2: There is no significant effect between recyclable packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.773 ^a	.598	.59	1.50291

a. Predictors: (Constant), Recyclable

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Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1210.485	1	1210.485	535.915	.000 ^b
	Residual	813.142	360	2.259		
	Total	2023.627	361			61

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer buying behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Recyclable

Table 6 :Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.373	.440		3.123	.002
	Recyclable packs	.855	.037	.773	23.150	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer buying behaviour

Source: *The Researcher's Computation (2023).*

Results on the table show that the independent variable Recyclable Packs ($X_2 = R_p$) explained approximately 60% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks with an $R^2 = 0.598$. This means that recyclable packs, considered as a green marketing indicator, were able to account for 60% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour. The result reveals that the relationship between Recyclable Packs (R_p) and consumer buying behaviour (C_b) was strong according to the $R = 0.773$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.597$, indicating that the regression model of this study is said to have a strong explanatory power of the dependent variable.

In addition, the F-ratio = 535.915 and p-value < 0.000 on the ANOVA suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that recyclable packs significantly predicted the changes in the dependent variable (consumer buying behaviour). To evaluate the degree of change between the independent variable and the

dependent variable, the value of the beta coefficients for Recyclable Packs (Rp) had a statistically significant unstandardised coefficient of $\beta_2 = 0.855$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.000$, indicating a positive significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks. This finding can be interpreted to mean that every unit change made in making the packs recyclable will result in a 0.855 increase in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks, all other factors being held constant. The resulting simple linear model is represented as as:

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_2 X_2 \dots + e$$

$$Y = 1.373 + 0.855 X_2$$

$$Cb = 1.373 + 0.855 Rp$$

Since the significant $p\text{-value}$ is less than 0.05 (Sig. $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$), it is concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between recyclable packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion

Findings from the first hypothesis test revealed a significant positive relationship between eco-friendly packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State, with a regression coefficient of $R^2 = 0.628$ and a $p\text{-value}$ of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. This indicates that the independent variable, X_1 (eco-friendly packs = Ef), explained approximately 63% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks. This implies that ecological elements of product packaging, such as the materials used, environmentally friendly features, and decomposable nature, affect consumer buying behaviour in the state. This finding contrasts with Ebhote (2019), whose study revealed no significant relationship between eco-labelling, eco-friendly packs, and competitive advantage. Conversely, Prihandono et al. (2020) found that eco-friendly labels and packs were significantly related to consumer purchase decisions for bottled water, recommending that bottled water manufacturers implement green marketing campaigns suited to both regional and global markets to improve sales performance.

Findings from the second hypothesis test showed a significant positive relationship between recyclable packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State, with a regression coefficient of $R^2 = 0.598$ and a $p\text{-value}$ of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. This indicates that the independent variable, X_4 (recyclable packs = Rp), accounted for 60% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour. This suggests that the use of recyclable or reusable organic packaging, particularly paper, glass, plastic,

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and cardboard, and to a lesser extent wood and aluminium, was perceived as a socially responsible initiative by drink companies, influencing consumer purchasing decisions. This finding aligns with Boateng (2019), who noted that the use of plastic, aluminium cans, and paper as packaging, which can either decompose or be recycled, could influence consumer buying behaviour while reducing reliance on glass bottle packaging.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's findings demonstrate that green marketing significantly influences consumer buying behaviour for packaged drinks. This implies that drink manufacturers employing green marketing strategies can shape consumer purchasing decisions by emphasising eco-friendly and recyclable packaging as healthy, environmentally responsible practices, thereby appealing to environmentally conscious consumers. It is concluded that eco-friendly packs and recyclable packs are significant predictors of consumer buying behaviour for packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

On the basis of the study's findings, it is recommended that:

- I. The significant positive influence of eco-friendly packs on consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks suggests that manufacturers should use biodegradable materials in packaging their products.
- ii. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that manufacturers of drinks should prioritise the use of recyclable materials for packaging, especially those made of plastics. This is because the quality of recycled plastic is another main factor that influences the market for products like drinks, and it causes little or no harm to the environment directly as well as the product itself.

Suggestions for Further Studies

This study has a number of observed limitations that should be addressed in further research studies. The domain of this research study was limited to consumers of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. However, further studies may adopt the variables used in this study to ascertain consumers' preferences for fast-moving consumer goods based on their package type. Such studies may even be undertaken to

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assess the quality implication of package materials used for consumables and also assess word-of-mouth information as a strategy for creating consumer awareness on green marketing.

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